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PREVALENCE AND PATTERNS OF ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS AMONG ELDERLY PEOPLE IN PORT HARCOURT, NIGERIA: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Oral health problems among elderly populations represent a growing public health concern, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa where community-based epidemiological data remain scarce. **Objective:** This study investigated the prevalence and patterns of oral health problems among elderly residents of Port Harcourt Local Government Area (PHLGA), Rivers State, Nigeria. **Methods:** A descriptive cross-sectional study design was employed. Using a four-stage multistage sampling technique, 420 elderly individuals aged 60 years and above were recruited from five communities across PHLGA. Data were collected using a validated semi-structured questionnaire

and analysed with IBM SPSS version 26 using descriptive statistic. **Results:** Over half of participants (53.8%, n=226) reported at least one oral health problem. Periodontal disease was the most prevalent specific condition (16.2%), followed by tooth loss (15.7%) and dental caries (12.4%). Dental pain was reported by 41.2% in the past year. Oral cancer was diagnosed in 3.1%. No participant reported complete tooth loss. Dental pain was the most frequently recurring complaint (28.8% regularly; 53.1% occasionally). Only 17.7% attended dental check-ups regularly. **Conclusions:** Oral health problems are highly prevalent among the elderly in Port Harcourt. Targeted preventive programmes, community-based dental health education, and improved access to dental care services are urgently needed for this population.

Keywords: oral health, elderly, prevalence, periodontal disease, dental caries, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Oral health is a fundamental component of overall health and quality of life. The World Health Organisation (WHO) defines good oral health as a state free from mouth and facial pain, oral infections, sores, tooth decay, tooth loss, and other disorders that limit an individual's capacity to bite, chew, smile, speak, and maintain psychosocial wellbeing.¹ Oral health is integral across every stage of life, from childhood through to old age.

Globally, dental caries affect approximately 3.58 billion people whilst periodontal diseases affect 20-50% of the world's population.² These conditions are disproportionately concentrated among older adults, in whom they are compounded by systemic disease, reduced self-care capacity, and limited access to dental services.³ Poor oral health in elderly individuals has been associated with cardiovascular disease, diabetes, respiratory disease, and adverse mental health outcomes.^{4, 5}

In Nigeria, studies have documented a significant oral health burden among the elderly.

Braimoh⁶ reported a tooth loss prevalence of 43.6% among elderly residents of Port Harcourt. Osadolor et al.⁷ found high rates of periodontal disease and dental caries among elderly patients in Enugu, whilst Akodu et al.⁸ documented that 46.6% of elderly patients in Lagos experienced oral discomfort. Despite these findings, community-based epidemiological data on the prevalence and patterns of oral health problems in Port Harcourt specifically remain limited.

This study aimed to determine the overall prevalence of oral health problems among elderly people in PHLGA, describe the specific types of conditions affecting them, and determine the frequency and patterns of these conditions over a two-year period.

Such data are essential to inform targeted interventions, guide healthcare planning, and support oral health policy development for elderly Nigerians.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in Port Harcourt Local Government Area (PHLGA), Rivers State, Nigeria. Port Harcourt is Nigeria's fifth largest city, comprising 20 administrative wards encompassing diverse urban and peri-urban communities. Cross-sectional designs are appropriate for estimating the prevalence and distribution of health

conditions at a defined point in time.^{10,11}

Study Population and Sample Size

The target population comprised individuals aged 60 years and above residing in PHLGA. Individuals with severe cognitive impairment or conditions

precluding informed consent were excluded. The sample size of 420 was calculated using the Cochran⁹ formula: $n = \frac{Z^2pq}{e^2}$, using a reference tooth loss prevalence of 43.6%,⁶ a 95% confidence level ($Z=1.96$), and a margin of error of 0.05, yielding a minimum of 378, adjusted to 420 after accounting for a 10% non-

response rate.

Sampling Technique

A four-stage multistage sampling technique was employed. In Stage 1, five wards were selected by simple random sampling from PHLGA's 20 wards. In Stage 2, one community per ward was selected by balloting: Ogbunabali, Port Harcourt Township, Nkpolu Oroworukwo Two, Elekahia, and Buloma/Amadi-Ama. In Stage 3, households were allocated proportionately across communities and selected systematically. In Stage 4, where multiple eligible elderly individuals existed in a selected household, one was recruited by simple random method.

Data Collection

Data were collected using a semi-structured questionnaire adapted from Braimoh⁶ and Vaddi et al.,¹² covering sociodemographic characteristics, oral health status, and frequency patterns of conditions over the past two years. Pre-testing was conducted on 42 participants (10%) outside the study area. Data collection was carried out by the researcher and trained research assistants.

Data Analysis

Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analysed using IBM SPSS version 26. Categorical variables were summarised using frequencies and percentages. Continuous variables were expressed as means and standard deviations.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the University of Port Harcourt Research Ethics Committee (UPH/CEREMAD/REC/MM94/004).

Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection. Confidentiality was maintained through use of unique codes in place of personal identifiers.

RESULTS

A total of 420 elderly participants were enrolled with a 100% response rate. The mean age was 68.12 +/- 3.911 years. The majority (73.8%) were aged 60-69 years and 26.2% were aged 70 years and above. Just over half (51.7%) were female. Most participants had formal education (93.6%),

lived in urban areas (93.6%), and were unemployed (67.9%).

Three-quarters (74.5%) were married. Full sociodemographic data are presented in Table I.

More than half of participants (53.8%, n=226) reported at least one oral health problem.

Periodontal disease was the most prevalent specific condition (16.2%), followed by tooth loss (15.7%) and dental caries (12.4%). Dental pain or discomfort in the past year was reported by 41.2% of participants. Oral cancer was diagnosed in 3.1%. Notably, no participant reported complete tooth loss (edentulism). Full prevalence data are presented in Table II. Among the 226 participants with oral health problems, dental pain was the most frequently recurring complaint: 28.8% experienced it regularly and 53.1% occasionally. Periodontal disease occurred regularly in 12.4% of affected participants and occasionally in 17.7%. Tooth loss was reported regularly by 17.7%. Only 17.7% of participants attended dental check-ups regularly, whilst 31.4% rarely or never did. Frequency patterns are presented in Table

III.

DISCUSSION

This study found a high overall prevalence of oral health problems (53.8%) among elderly residents of Port Harcourt, with periodontal disease, dental pain, and tooth loss constituting the dominant conditions. These findings are consistent with and contribute to the growing body of evidence documenting the substantial oral health burden in elderly Nigerian populations. The overall prevalence of 53.8% is consistent with comparable studies. Braimoh⁶ documented a 43.6% prevalence of tooth loss alone among elderly Port Harcourt residents, whilst Osadolor et al.⁷ found high rates of periodontal disease and dental caries among elderly Nigerians in Enugu. AlZarea¹³ found that 74.2% of elderly Saudi Arabians had gum problems and 78.7% had missing teeth — rates higher than those observed in the present study, likely reflecting differences in study methodology and the use of clinical rather than self-reported assessment. The finding that all participants with no formal

education reported oral health problems underscores the critical role of education in enabling preventive behaviours and healthcare navigation.

Periodontal disease emerged as the most prevalent specific condition (16.2%), consistent with global evidence. Eke et al.¹⁴ found that more than 62% of older adults in the United States had clinical attachment loss indicative of severe periodontitis. The lower rate in the present study likely reflects the reliance on self-reporting, which may underestimate true clinical prevalence. Nazir¹⁸ reported global periodontal disease prevalence of 20-50%, with older adults bearing a disproportionate share of this burden.

The 41.2% prevalence of dental pain in the past year is particularly notable. Dental pain is a primary driver of healthcare-seeking behaviour and oral health impact on quality of life. However, the pattern analysis revealed that only 17.7% of affected participants attended dental check-ups regularly, whilst 31.4% rarely or never did. This pattern of reactive rather

than preventive care — seeking treatment only when pain becomes unbearable — is well documented in low- and middle-income country (LMIC) contexts and contributes to progression of oral conditions to more severe stages.^{16,17} Liu et al.¹⁷ demonstrated that regular dental visits are strongly associated with better oral health outcomes and quality of life in older adults.

The absence of edentulism in this sample,

despite a 15.7% prevalence of partial tooth loss, may reflect the relatively younger mean age of participants (68.12 years) or indicate that tooth loss has not yet progressed to complete dentition loss in this cohort. This differs from Eke et al.,¹⁴ who found 19% edentulism among older US adults, potentially reflecting differences in age distribution, access to preventive care, and dietary patterns.

A key strength of this study is its large,

community-based, randomly sampled population with a 100% response rate, providing data representative of the broader elderly population of PHLGA. Limitations include the cross-sectional design, which precludes causal inference, and reliance on self-reported data, which may be subject to recall and social desirability biases. The absence of clinical oral examinations means that true clinical prevalence of conditions such as periodontal disease may be

underestimated. Future studies should incorporate clinical assessments and

longitudinal designs.

CONCLUSION

Oral health problems are highly prevalent among elderly people in Port Harcourt, with over half of participants affected by at least one condition. Periodontal disease, dental pain, and tooth loss constitute the primary burden, whilst dental care utilisation remains low. These findings highlight the urgent need for integrated, communitybased

oral health programmes targeting the elderly in Port Harcourt and similar urban Nigerian settings. Strengthening outreach by dental professionals, integrating oral health screening into routine geriatric checks, and developing policy frameworks that ensure affordable and accessible dental care for elderly populations are strongly recommended.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Table I: Sociodemographic Characteristics of Study Participants (n=420)

Variable	Frequency (n=420)	Percentage (%)
Age category		
60-69 years	310	73.8
70 years and above	110	26.2
Mean age +/- SD = 68.12 +/- 3.911 years		
Gender		
Male	203	48.3
Female	217	51.7
Education level		
Formal education	393	93.6
No formal education	27	6.4
Occupation		
Business/farming/tailoring/others	258	61.4
Civil servant/engineering	162	38.6
Monthly income		
Less than or equal to N50,000	150	35.7
Greater than N50,000	270	64.3
Employment status		
Employed	135	32.1
Unemployed	285	67.9
Marital status		
Married	313	74.5
Unmarried	107	25.5
Residential area		
Urban	393	93.6
Rural	27	6.4

SD = Standard Deviation

Table II: Prevalence of Oral Health Problems Among Elderly People in Port Harcourt

(n=420)

Oral Health Problem	Frequency (n=420)	Percentage (%)
Overall (at least one problem)		
Yes	226	53.8
No	194	46.2
Dental caries (tooth decay)		
Yes	52	12.4
No	368	87.6
Periodontal disease (gum disease)		
Yes	68	16.2
No	352	83.8
Tooth loss		
Yes	66	15.7
No	354	84.3
Dental pain or discomfort (past year)		
Yes	173	41.2
No	247	58.8

Oral cancer diagnosis

Yes

13

3.1

No 407 96.9 **Table III: Frequency Patterns of Oral Health Problems Among Elderly People in Port Harcourt (n=226)**

Condition	Regularly n (%)	Occasionally n (%)	Rarely/Never n (%)
Dental caries	10 (4.4%)	38 (16.8%)	178 (78.8%)
Periodontal disease	28 (12.4%)	40 (17.7%)	158 (69.9%)
Tooth loss	40 (17.7%)	26 (11.5%)	160 (70.8%)
Dental pain/discomfort	65 (28.8%)	120 (53.1%)	41 (18.1%)
Oral cancer	9 (4.0%)	3 (1.3%)	214 (94.7%)
Dental check-up visits	40 (17.7%)	115 (50.9%)	71 (31.4%)

Percentages are calculated among the 226 participants who reported at least one oral health problem.